

Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Mercury(II) using Diphenylthiocarbazide

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Mercury is a well-known source of water pollution. Detection and estimation of mercury at the ppm level constitute an important aspect in water pollution control programmes. Solvent extraction methods are important in this field and ion-association complexes are increasingly investigated. The method reported here is based on the extraction of a red complex formed by Hg^{II} with diphenylthiocarbazide (DPTC). The system is very simple and almost as sensitive as that reported by De and Pal¹. Moreover, the method suffers least interferences. Microgram quantities of mercury can be estimated in presence of commonly associated water pollutants like lead, cadmium, zinc, copper etc. Previous use of the reagent has been made to determine copper².

Results and Discussion

The complex exhibits absorption maximum at 490 nm, where the absorbance of the reagent blank is very small. The system conforms to Beer's law over 8 ppm of mercury. The molar absorptivity of the complex, based on the metal content, was evaluated to be $(1.83-2.05) \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with Sandell's sensitivity $0.009 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ at 490 nm.

The effect of acidity on the extractibility of mercury was examined in terms of absorbance of the complex. The complex exhibited constant and maximum absorbance when the extractions were carried out at pH 0.5-3.0. In each case, the aqueous phase after extraction, was clear and colourless. When the operation was repeated using the same aqueous phase left after a single extraction, the organic extract virtually showed no absorbance. This indicated a complete and quantitative extraction of the metal in the aforesaid acidity range.

It has been found that 0.25 ml of 0.4% acetone solution of DPTC was sufficient to extract $40 \mu\text{g}$ of Hg^{II} . In practice, 0.5 ml of the reagent was preferred as a part of the added reagent might be consumed if the foreign ions were present.

Apart from chloroform, some other solvents like 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE), ethyl acetate, benzene and carbon tetrachloride were tested as extracting solvents, but those offered no special advantages over chloroform. The spectral curves of the organic extracts taken against the respective reagent blanks were identical in nature. In case of DCE or CCl_4 , the corresponding reagent blanks showed considerable absorbance in the region.

In order to study the effects of diverse ions on the extraction behaviour, $40 \mu\text{g}$ of mercury were

extracted and determined according to the recommended procedure in presence of the respective foreign ions. An ion was considered to interfere if the recovery of mercury differed by more than $\pm 3\%$ from the actual amount taken. A 50-fold excess of Al^{III} , Ba^{II} , Be^{II} , Co^{II} , Cr^{III} , La^{III} , Mn^{II} , Sn^{II} , U^{VI} , Fe^{III} and Ca^{II} , and a 25-fold excess of Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} , Mg^{II} , Mo^{VI} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} , Rh^{III} , Sr^{II} , Th^{IV} and Zn^{II} did not interfere. Vanadium(V) interfered. Among the anions tested, a 100-fold excess of fluoride, phosphate, acetate, tartrate, ascorbate, arsenate, EDTA, thiocyanate, citrate and oxalate had no adverse effects. The system showed low tolerance limits for iodide and bromide. However, thiosulphate and thiourea must be absent.

The precision and accuracy of the proposed method were tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of mercury. The average of six determinations of $40 \mu\text{g}$ Hg was found to be $39.8 \mu\text{g} \pm 0.40$ (std. dev.) with the relative mean deviation of 2.4%. Thus the method is fairly precise and reproducible. The total time needed for each run is 10-15 min. The proposed method is comparable with some other existing method shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF THE PRESENT METHOD WITH OTHER METHODS

Reagent	λ_{max} nm	Molar absorptivity $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Remarks
Crystal violet and iodide ^a	545	2.3×10^5	Hg determined in industrial waters
Brilliant green and iodide ^b	680	6.3×10^4	Hg determined in ores and waste waters
Malachite green and iodide ^c	630	8.7×10^4	Fe^{III} masked with fluoride and Bi^{III} with EDTA
Methyl violet and iodide ^c	600	7.1×10^4	
Present method	490	$(1.83-2.05) \times 10^4$	V ^V , thiosulphate and thiourea interfere

*aRef. 6. ^bRef. 7. ^cRef. 1.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu PR-1 spectrophotometer.

A stock solution of Hg^{II} was prepared from HgCl_2 and the solution was standardised³; a working solution of Hg^{II} (80 ppm) was prepared by appropriate dilution. DPTC was prepared as repor-

ted⁴. Buffer solution (pH 1), prepared from KCl-HCl⁵, was used to adjust the acidity of the aqueous solution. Chloroform and other organic solvents were distilled before use. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their corresponding salts. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 40 µg of Hg^{II}, was added a 0.4% acetic solution of DPTC (0.5 ml) followed by buffer (5 ml). It was then diluted to 10 ml with distilled water and left for 1 min to ensure complete complexation. Finally it was equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) for 1 min. The separated organic layer was shaken with anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove any retained water. The absorbance of the organic extract was measured at 490 nm against the reagent blank and

the amount of mercury determined. To study the effects of diverse ions, the respective foreign ions were added to the aqueous sample solution before addition of the reagent.

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